

ARTICLE INFO

©2025 RS Publication

Paper ID: AJSCS-
68ECA93647F4A

Published: 2026-01-09

DOI:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18199538>

Page No: 9-21

GIG ECONOMY SHIFTS: SOCIAL CHANGES AND LABOUR DYNAMICS AMONG MARGINALISED COMMUNITIES IN NORTH CHENNAI'S DIGITALISED WORKFORCE

JAYASURYA. K

Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Social Work, Loyola College, Chennai,
Tamil Nadu, India.

Dr. J.M. ARUL KAMARAJ

Research Guide, Department of Social Work, Loyola College, Chennai,
Tamil Nadu, India.

ABSTRACT

By giving rise to the gig economy, the technological growth of the digital era has reshaped the world of work. Though engaged by the registered companies, gig workers in India are classified as unorganised labourers, a status recognised by the Government of Tamil Nadu. This study explores the social changes affecting marginalised communities involved in platform-based occupations (e.g., Swiggy, Rapido) in North Chennai. Using a qualitative case study approach with ten in-depth interviews, observation, and document analysis, the research reveals significant power imbalances and a policy–practice disconnect. Findings show that while gig work enables higher daily earnings, yet it comes with long-term insecurity and lack of savings. Applications algorithms impose workers into “forced labour,” pushing them to remain continuously available during peak hours and weekends, causing both physical strain and family conflict. Despite awareness of state welfare schemes (e.g., e-scooter subsidy, insurance), workers reported ineffective implementation, communication gaps, and delays in accessing benefits. customers ill- treatments further expose the absence of formal grievance mechanisms, highlighting a modern form of exploitation where corporations profit from a vulnerable,

Cite This Paper: JAYASURYA. K. AND Dr. J.M. ARUL KAMARAJ (2026). "GIG ECONOMY SHIFTS: SOCIAL CHANGES AND LABOUR DYNAMICS AMONG MARGINALISED COMMUNITIES IN NORTH CHENNAI'S DIGITALISED WORKFORCE". AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SUSTAINABLE CITY AND SOCIETY (AJSCS), vol. 16, no. 1, 2026, pp. 9-21. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18199538>

unorganised workforce. The study raises for multi-pronged interventions, including reducing commissions or raising fees by platforms, strengthening government implementation and communication of social security measures, and exploring publicly run gig platforms that ensure fair practices. Overall, this research provides localised evidence on the precarious realities of gig workers in North Chennai and offers actionable insights to promote fair and sustainable livelihoods for marginalised digital workers in urban India.

Key words: *Digitalisation, Gig Economy, Labour Precarity, Marginalised Communities, Chennai, Platform Economy, Social Security Gaps, Tamil Nadu, Unorganised Workers, Welfare Implementation.*

INTRODUCTION

The technological development of the digital era has reconfigured the world of work, giving rise to new forms of employment and labour dynamics, particularly evident in the burgeoning gig economy. This sector is a paradoxical force, contributing significantly to a country's economy while providing a flexible but often unstable livelihood for its workers. It democratises job opportunities, allowing anyone with a smartphone and basic skills to be employed after a brief onboarding process. However, the working conditions are highly prone to uncertainty, as these workers are legally classified as unorganised by the Union and Tamil Nadu governments, as per the Code on Social Security, 2020 (CoSS, 2020) and the e-Shram portal. Yet, they work for registered companies like Zomato, Swiggy, Uber, and Rapido, with their relationship and benefits starkly different from those of regular employees. At the national level, the government plans to offer benefits to gig workers under the Code on Social Security, 2020. The Tamil Nadu government has also included gig workers in the Tamil Nadu Manual Workers Act of 1982, a law that covers 19 other groups of workers from unorganised sectors, such as construction workers, washermen, and tailors. While the gig economy's impact is widely discussed at a national level, less attention has been paid to how its shifts specifically affect vulnerable populations in urban contexts. This study addresses that gap by exploring the profound social changes and labour dynamics impacting the lives and livelihoods of marginalised communities engaged in digital platform-based occupations in North Chennai, Tamil Nadu. This research will delve into the unique challenges faced by these workers, whose existing vulnerabilities are often amplified by the precarity inherent in this new form of employment.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The Code explicitly defines "gig workers" (those outside the traditional employer-employee setup) and "platform workers" (a subset dependent on digital platforms) and includes measures for their social security. The gig economy, driven by digital platforms, has emerged as a significant source of employment, yet it operates largely outside the traditional labour framework. While it offers flexible work opportunities, it introduces a unique set of vulnerabilities for workers, who are not recognised as formal employees and thus lack access to stable income, social security, and standard labour rights. This precarity is particularly pronounced among marginalised communities, who often turn to gig work due to limited access to traditional employment and are more susceptible to financial instability and exploitation. Despite the growing number of gig workers in India, especially in major urban centres like Chennai, there is a critical lack of research specifically focused on the challenges faced by marginalised communities in North Chennai. These workers often navigate a dual challenge: the systemic disadvantages tied to their socio-economic backgrounds and the inherent uncertainties of the gig economy. The existing government policies, while a step in the right direction, may not fully address the nuanced issues of implementation and access for these specific communities. Therefore, a comprehensive understanding of the socio-economic conditions, labour dynamics, and policy gaps impacting this vulnerable workforce is essential to propose effective and equitable solutions.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Almayanda Alauddin et al. (2025) emphasise that while flexibility and autonomy initially attract gig workers, digital platforms increasingly exercise control through client evaluations and algorithmic management. Penalties for missed deadlines and excessive working hours, often exceeding 10–12 hours daily, reduce social support, psychological well-being, and work enthusiasm, resulting in burnout. Stern surveillance, restrictions on break times, and blurred work–life boundaries further undermine autonomy and strain family relationships. Most workers feel this arbitrary supervision is unfair and disrespectful, and they are left with a greatly reduced sense of autonomy. Most workers feel this arbitrary supervision is unfair and disrespectful, and they are left with a greatly reduced sense of autonomy.

Behl et al. (2022) found high competition, long wait times, and late-night deliveries are barriers for gig workers because they have high driving power and low dependence that dictate overall

working conditions. Payment arrangements and prohibitive conditions related to earning incentives are linked and indicate moderate driving power and dependence, adding to the complexities of the worker's economic stability. In comparison, recurring expenses for gig workers, like internet, fuel, and vehicle maintenance, show high dependence, and low driving power; in the described context, they are not nearly as meaningful when looking through the lens of larger structural and systemic barriers.

Waldkirch et al. (2021) explain that from the HRM perspective, training and development, access and mobility, appraisal and control, scoring and feedback, and platform literacy and support are vital propositions for enhancing gig workers' skills and employability. Besides being relevant to employability, these measures are valuable in increasing motivation, engagement, and long-term satisfaction at digital labour platforms. By institutionalising such HRM practices, platforms can alleviate worker vulnerabilities and provide for more sustainable career development opportunities.

Berger et al. (2019) illustrated that although they had fewer earnings, Uber drivers experienced higher subjective well-being due to their flexibility and autonomy. The ability to choose their work hours and manage their personal schedules was perceived as a central element of appeal in platform work. Individual drivers ranked their pay as modest, but when questioned about their experiences, they affiliated flexibility with a sense of independence, contributing positively to their overall satisfaction with life. This evidence demonstrates that non-monetary features of gig work shape worker perceptions and engagement.

Kurian and Bindu Madhavi (2024) acknowledge that the gig economy provides employment for the short term, and the great advancement in digitization has resulted in innovative flexible forms of digital work, which can engage both high and low-skilled labour. The study examined the extent to which motivation and challenges of gig work influences quality of life, stress, and well-being for gig workers. The study revealed that control of schedule, extra income, flexibility of time, and entry level work provided positive incentives that motivated gig workers. Ultimately, motivation served as a significant variable impacting gig workers' perceptions of quality of life and well-being, with financial rewards and psychological security being two critical factors influencing service engagement and satisfaction for service workers using a platform.

NEED AND IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

Filling a Research Gap: While many studies exist on the gig economy, this research is unique because it focuses on the intersection of the gig economy and marginalised communities in a specific urban context: North Chennai. This will provide a more detailed and localised understanding of the challenges, moving beyond broad, national-level analyses.

Informing Policy and Practice: By assessing existing government policies in Tamil Nadu, this study will identify the specific gaps in implementation that prevent schemes from benefiting the most vulnerable workers. The findings will provide actionable data for policymakers to design more effective social protection measures.

Advocating for Worker Rights: The research will shed light on the lived experiences of marginalised gig workers, including issues of precarity, lack of welfare access, and labour rights violations. This data can serve as a powerful tool for NGOs, unions, and community leaders to advocate for fairer working conditions and better social security.

Contributing to Sustainable Development: As the gig economy grows, understanding its impact on vulnerable populations is vital. The study's recommendations for inclusive strategies will help ensure that the digital transformation of work benefits all parts of society, rather than deepening existing inequalities.

OBJECTIVES

- To analyse the socio-economic conditions of marginalised gig workers in North Chennai.
- To investigate the evolving work and relational dynamics within gig economy platforms for these communities.
- To critically examine challenges in income stability, welfare access, and labour rights for marginalised gig workers.
- To assess the effectiveness of existing government policies and social protection measures for this workforce in Tamil Nadu.
- To propose inclusive strategies and policy recommendations for equitable and sustainable gig livelihoods

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative case study methodology to explore the social and labour dynamics of the gig economy. The approach is suitable for investigating this contemporary issue within its real-world context.

The researcher used non-probability purposive sampling to select 10 respondents from the marginalised gig workforce in North Chennai. The sample size was limited based on the concept of theoretical saturation, as no new insights were being generated. The selected respondents had at least six months of experience in fields like food delivery or ride-hailing.

Data will be collected using three primary methods: in-depth interviews, direct observation of work routines, and document analysis of government policies and company materials. This combination of methods will ensure data triangulation, which adds to the reliability and validity of the research findings. The overall methodology aims to generate a comprehensive understanding of the issue to inform policy and practice.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Case Study 1: Primary Rapido Driver

A 29-year-old married man from a Scheduled Caste (SC) community, this respondent is a Rapido driver in North Chennai. He chose this gig as his primary source of income due to its flexibility. His financial situation is precarious, with no savings, which he attributes to his family's lack of assets and his parents' low educational status. He reports that his financial insecurity is exacerbated when compared to other communities. He views his work as impersonal and independent, facing challenges with technological updates due to a lack of training. He is unaware of any welfare schemes and feels vulnerable to violations due to his unfamiliarity with labour rights. He believes there is a significant gap in the government's schemes reaching the ground level and suggests that a gig workers' union and government intervention are necessary to ensure fair practices.

Case Study 2: Former Gig Worker

A 29-year-old man from a Scheduled Caste (SC) community, and an SSLC holder, this respondent was a gig driver and the sole breadwinner for his mother. He could earn around ₹1,000 per day but was unable to save, which became his primary concern and led him to seek a job with a monthly salary. He notes that platform algorithms now prioritise continuous work,

which creates pressure to work during peak hours and on weekends, impacting his personal life. He views this as a form of "forced labour" and feels isolated from a peer network. While aware of government schemes, he highlights a significant gap in their implementation in North Chennai. He has faced ill-treatment from customers and suggests that the government should create its own public sector-run gig application.

Case Study 3: College Graduate in Gig Work

A 23-year-old unmarried man from a Backward Class (BC) community with a college degree, this respondent began gig work as a leisure pursuit that has now become his primary income source. He earns enough for daily expenses but is unable to save. He finds the work less stressful than a traditional job, but he criticises the lack of a formal grievance mechanism for customer ill-treatment. He feels that the influx of many educated temporary workers affects his opportunities and income stability. He is aware of government schemes but believes their implementation is minimal in North Chennai. He also notes that he has faced mistreatment from customers and has been denied access to hotel restrooms and main gates.

Case Study 4: Converted Gig Worker

This 29-year-old unmarried graduate from a Most Backward Class (MBC) community previously worked for multiple gig platforms but has since transitioned to a traditional job for better savings and social status. He found gig work to be flexible and accurate, and he was not concerned about peak-hour or weekend work due to his lack of personal commitments. He felt that the influx of educated workers into the gig economy contributed to income fluctuations and financial insecurity. While aware of government schemes, he said their implementation in North Chennai was low, lounges were not properly operated, and the e-scooter subsidy came with the burden of EMI payments. He believed that there was a huge communication gap between the government and gig workers and recommended that platforms reduce commissions and that the government address fake online advertisements.

Case Study 5: Student Gig Worker

A 24-year-old man from a Backward Class (BC) community, this degree holder uses gig work part-time to cover his expenses while pursuing a diploma. He feels comfortable with the flexibility of the work but has no separate savings. He notes that the influx of educated workers into the gig economy affects his opportunities and contributes to income fluctuations. He also highlights the burden of the cash-on-delivery system, as he is held responsible for cancelled

orders, which can lead to financial losses. He is aware of government schemes but has little interest in them due to the perceived barriers in implementation and communication. He recommends that companies increase delivery charges and reduce their platform commissions.

Case Study 6: Family Man

A 38-year-old married man from a Scheduled Caste (SC) community with two children, this degree holder is the sole breadwinner for his family. He finds gig work less stressful and better paid than traditional jobs but is unable to save. He worries that platform algorithms, which give preference to consistent workers, conflict with his family commitments. He feels that the mandatory work during peak hours and on weekends feels like "forced labour." He is aware of government schemes but notes that their implementation is poor and that there is a lag in claiming benefits. He recommends that the government monitor the industry and address the issue of fake online advertisements.

Case Study 7: MBA Holder

This 24-year-old unmarried man from a Scheduled Caste (SC) community, with an MBA degree, uses gig work as a part-time job. He finds the work flexible and less stressful than a core job. He is aware of welfare schemes but feels that there are significant barriers to their implementation and communication. He also mentioned a lag in claiming benefits. While he reports no caste or gender discrimination, he has been ill-treated by customers and feels that mandatory weekend work is a labour rights violation. He is unaware of the specific schemes in Tamil Nadu but feels that the overall implementation of policies is very low in North Chennai. He recommends that platforms increase delivery charges and provide proper respect to workers.

Case Study 8: SSLC Holder

A 26-year-old unmarried man from a Scheduled Caste (SC) community, this SSLC holder uses gig work with Shadowfax as a side job. He feels that platform algorithms make him "less preferred" if he takes a break, and that low per-kilometre charges and mandatory peak-hour work feel like "forced labour." He is aware of government schemes but was unable to benefit from them and notes that their implementation is low. He also felt physically exhausted from the work. He believes the government should monitor the industry and consider launching a separate public sector-run gig platform to prevent exploitation.

Case Study 9: Traditional Auto Driver

A 41-year-old married man from a Scheduled Caste (SC) community is a professional auto-rickshaw driver who uses Rapido as a secondary job. He feels that platform algorithms make him less preferred if he skips orders and that his traditional way of bargaining has been destroyed by gig platforms. He is aware of government schemes but feels that their implementation is low. He believes the government should monitor the industry and consider launching a separate public sector-run gig platform to protect workers from what he sees as corporate exploitation.

Case Study 10: Part-Time Gig Worker for Extra Income

A 29-year-old man from a Most Backward Class (MBC) community with a degree, this respondent works for platforms as a part-time job to earn additional income. He is not worried about platform algorithms but feels that there is no formal mechanism to address customer ill-treatment. He is aware of welfare schemes but feels that there are significant barriers to their implementation and communication. He believes that the government should form its own platform to control and allot orders to workers and resolve conflicts between gig workers and traditional auto-rickshaw drivers.

DISCUSSION

The findings from these case studies reveal a paradoxical reality for marginalised gig workers in North Chennai. While the gig economy offers a flexible source of income, it exposes them to significant vulnerabilities and labour precarity. The results varies pertaining to the different platforms and its users.

Socio-Economic Conditions and Lived Experiences

Respondents from various educational backgrounds view gig work as a viable alternative to traditional jobs, which they feel offer insufficient pay. While daily earnings often surpass a core job's salary, this comes at the cost of long-term financial stability, as all respondents reported being unable to save. The influx of highly educated workers seeking temporary work increases competition and contributes to income fluctuations for those who depend on gig work as their primary livelihood.

Work Dynamics and Labour Precarity

A key finding is the significant power imbalance between workers and platforms. Algorithms assign work based on a worker's continuity, creating pressure to work during peak hours and weekends. Several respondents described this as "forced labour" and noted that non-compliance leads to less work. Interactions with platforms and customers are impersonal, with no formal grievance mechanism to address issues like ill-treatment. Workers are often left to handle problems themselves, from dealing with drunk customers to being responsible for cancelled cash-on-delivery orders. Physical strain and fatigue from long hours and low pay were also common complaints.

Awareness and Access to Welfare Measures

The findings show a stark contrast between government intentions and the ground realities of policy implementation. While all respondents were aware of Tamil Nadu's initiatives, such as the e-scooter subsidy, insurance, and lounges, they felt their implementation in North Chennai was minimal or ineffective. A major finding is the significant communication gap, with workers feeling that information about these schemes is not reaching them through proper channels. This lack of effective implementation contributes to a general lack of trust and interest in government support.

Recommendations and Future Outlook

The respondents proposed several strategies for a more equitable gig economy. Their key recommendations include increasing per-kilometre charges and reducing platform commissions. Many also suggested that the government should intervene to monitor the industry and consider launching its own public sector-run gig application. The findings also point to the need for platforms and the government to address issues like fake online advertisements, which lead to disputes between customers and delivery agents. Finally, a number of respondents felt that a dedicated gig workers' union should be established to collectively voice their issues.

SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- Implement a robust grievance system: Platforms should create accessible channels for workers to report issues like customer ill-treatment or payment disputes.

- Enhance digital training: Platforms should offer targeted training on app features to ensure all workers, regardless of their background, can use the technology effectively.
- Increase earnings and reduce commissions: Platforms should raise per-kilometre charges and reduce their commission fees to ensure fair pay and a more stable income.
- Improve welfare policy implementation: The government should ensure better implementation and communication of its schemes in North Chennai. This includes properly operating lounges and using channels like apps and phone calls to inform workers.
- Form a dedicated gig workers' union: A union should be established to give workers a collective voice to negotiate for better rights and working conditions.
- Launch a government-run platform: The government should consider launching its own gig platform to ensure fairer practices and provide an alternative to corporate platforms.
- Address fake online advertisements: The government and platforms should work together to monitor and reduce fake online advertisements from unauthorised sellers. These ads lead to disputes between customers and delivery agents when the customer finds the product is of low quality or fake.
- Ensure timely benefits claims: Authorities should address the lag in claiming benefits like insurance, ensuring a smooth and timely process for workers in need.
- Promote an inclusive work culture: Platform companies should treat gig workers with respect, providing them with resources and opportunities to foster loyalty and a sense of belonging.
- Resolve conflicts with traditional workers: The government should step in to resolve conflicts between gig workers and traditional auto-rickshaw drivers, as the gig economy is affecting their traditional business.

CONCLUSION

The gig economy presents a complex landscape where problems vary depending on the work, platform, and customer interactions. As evidenced by this study, these issues are not uniform: while traditional auto-rickshaw drivers feel that platforms have destroyed their profession, students and young graduates see gig work as a temporary solution for their immediate financial needs. For customers, the model is user-friendly, cheap, and provides immediate solutions, with their problems often being quickly rectified.

However, behind this convenience lies a significant concern for the workers. Issues such as high platform commissions, job uncertainty, and the lack of permanent social security measures after retirement persist. This digital form of employment, which provides jobs, still classifies these individuals as unorganised workers, even as they work for major corporations. This paradox highlights a modern form of exploitation. Addressing these challenges requires a collective effort, with the government, companies, and society working together to ensure that the gig economy's digital solutions do not come at the expense of its workforce.

REFERENCES

- Almayanda Alauddin, F. D., Aman, A., Ghazali, M. F., & Daud, S. (2025). The influence of digital platforms on gig workers: A systematic literature review. *Heliyon*, *11*(1), e41491. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e41491>
- Behl, A., Rajagopal, K., Sheorey, P., & Mahendra, A. (2022). Barriers to entry of gig workers in the gig platforms: Exploring the dark side of the gig economy. *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, *74*(5), 818–839. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJIM-08-2021-0235>
- De Ruyter, A., & Brown, M. (2019). Regulation and the lived experience of the gig economy. In *The gig economy* (pp. 55–78). Agenda Publishing. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctvnjbf3.6>
- Dinakaran. (2025, January). Namakkal, Karur, Cuddalore – New food delivery app introduced. <https://www.dinakaran.com/news/namakkal-karur-cuddalore-new-food-delivery-app-introduced>
- Financial Express. (2025, January 15). Zomato, Swiggy test higher platform fees in select cities. <https://www.financialexpress.com/business/industry-zomato-swiggy-test-higher-platform-fees-in-select-cities-3965900>
- Ghosh, A. (2020). *GIG ECONOMY IN INDIA RISING: GEN X-Millennial-Z* (1st ed.). Evincepub Publishing.
- Kurian, J. S., & Bindu Madhavi, N. (2024). Navigating the gig economy: Exploring challenges and motivations for the wellbeing of Gen Y and Gen Z gig workers. *Cogent Psychology*, *11*(1), 2357458. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311908.2024.2357458>

- Singh, H. (2024). Gig workers: A comprehensive analysis of the rise, challenges, and future of the gig economy. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 6(5), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.36948/ijfmr.2024.v06i05.29525>
- The Hindu. (2025, March 12). A gig that provides and traps. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/tamil-nadu/a-gig-that-provides-and-traps/article69334987.ece>
- The Hindu. (2025, August 28). Shunning Swiggy, Zomato: Namakkal restaurant owners move to Tamil Nadu-based online food delivery platform Zaaroz. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/tamil-nadu/shunning-swiggy-zomato-namakkal-restaurant-owners-move-to-tamil-nadu-based-online-food-delivery-platform-zaaroz/article69783246.ece>
- The Hindu. (2025, September 3). Platform fees now an industry standard, an inevitable development. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/platform-fees-now-an-industry-standard-an-inevitable-development/article69823248.ece>
- Times of India. (2025, January 20). Just 7% of TN's gig workers signed up for welfare scheme. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/chennai/just-7-of-tns-gig-workers-signed-up-for-welfare-scheme/articleshow/122270974.cms>
- Times of India. (2025, February 28). TN boosts gig economy welfare: ₹20k e-scooter subsidy cleared, group insurance for 50,000 workers. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/chennai/tn-boosts-gig-economy-welfare-rs-20k-e-scooter-subsidy-cleared-group-insurance-for-50000-workers/articleshow/123156106.cms>
- Tiwari, A., Khan, S., Chandran, R., & Tewari, A. (2024). Investigating the primary factors of work happiness in gig workers. *Employee Relations: The International Journal*, 46(5), 1112–1140. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ER-07-2023-0369>
- Vasudevan, V. (2025). *OTP please: Online buyers, sellers and gig workers in South Asia*. Penguin Random House India Private Limited.